

China Economic Strategy after the Pandemic World Crisis

Forewords

The economical crisis that fall in 2020 with the COVID19 gave the opportunity to China to accelerate the strategy of domination of world economy.

Actually China is buying companies and land in sales price because world economies are completely struggled by this pandemic.

It is very important people to know about the schemes and how financial operations are preceded.

Introduction

Between 1980 and 2010, according to World Bank data, the average annual growth of the world economy was 2.82%.

In the late 1980s, Deng Xiaoping (1987) said that:

“On the whole, our goals are not too ambitious. We give ourselves 20 years -- that is, from 1981 to the end of the century -- to quadruple our GNP and achieve comparative prosperity, with an annual per capita GNP of US\$800 to \$1,000. Then we shall take that figure as a new starting point and try to quadruple it again, so as to reach a per capita GNP of \$4,000 in another 50 years. What does this mean? It means that by the middle of the next century we hope to reach the level of the moderately developed countries. If we can achieve this goal, first, we shall have accomplished a tremendous task; second, we shall have made a real contribution to mankind; and third, we shall have demonstrated more convincingly the superiority of the socialist system. As our principle of distribution is a socialist one, our per capita GNP of \$4,000 will be different from the equivalent amount in the capitalist countries. For one thing, China has a huge population.

If we assume that by the mid-21st century our population will have reached 1.5 billion and that we shall have a per capita GNP of \$4,000, then our total annual GNP will be \$6 trillion, and that will place China in the front ranks of nations.

When we reach that goal, we shall not only have blazed a new path for the peoples of the Third World, who represent three quarters of the world's population, but also -- and this is even more important -- we shall have demonstrated to mankind that socialism is the only path and that it is superior to capitalism.”

Thirty years earlier than predicted by Deng Xiaoping, as at the end of 2010 the per capita incomecapita had already been more than doubled and could quadruple in 2020.

It is still what level will be reached by per capita income in 2050.

China today stands as an emerging economy to push the limits imposed by developed capitalist nations. Attention is drawn in particular to its efforts to ensure high rates of economic growth from the endogenous diffusion of innovation processes in urban and rural activities and by incorporating an increasing volume of Chinese into a pattern of consumption similar to the middle classes residing in the most advanced countries industrially.

Additionally, the gigantic volume of international reserves that comes accumulating, as a result of its export strategy and economic integration, place the Chinese economy as a powerful lever for diversified investments in various regions of the world. From an internal point of view, they make it possible to a Sovereign Fund and the maintenance of financing lines from the largest State development bank in operation, powerfully feeding its prospects of becoming a great power superior to the USA, thus removing its hegemony.

Since the late 1970s, the Chinese government has adopted the son-in-law policy unique as a way of containing the country's population growth. According to this politics, each couple, in urban centres, could only have one child and, in the countryside, the rule could be modified if the couple's first child was female.

The business of buying

About 30 years later the Chinese central government took a positive view of the policy.

In view of the country's Central Population and Family Planning Commission, this policy prevented nearly 400 million births from occurring in the period consideration.

Since the adoption of this policy, one of the main concerns of the government Chinese, even though numerous developments in population growth could listed, concerns the country's food supply capacity and prospects for expanding this offer.

Over the years the Chinese population maintained a natural decreasing rate of growth, with absolute growth of the total population of more than 30%, China faces numerous natural and climatic difficulties to ensure an adequate supply of food to its population.

The prospect of expansion of the cultivated area has been practically null for some centuries, both because of geographical conditions and for its former territorial occupation and expansion of the agricultural frontier, as well as its vast population.

Thus, the recent process of land acquisition in other countries is an important piece of this puzzle, being intrinsically associated with its population dynamics, its transformations and the impacts that these phenomena generate on the needs of country provision.

The measures adopted to meet the internal demand for natural resources are varied, but land and business acquisitions abroad are an important indicator of the Chinese need for such resources and their guarantee strategy autonomy in the internal supply of raw materials and food sovereignty.

Furthermore, the potential supply problems generated by political changes supplier countries or their relations with China itself also contribute for the expansion of the own production chain of Chinese companies in some sectors and countries.

Land purchases by China and other countries in the world It is difficult to trace the exact origin of land acquisitions worldwide, since, as much as the host country of the investment is registered, it is often a matter of a tangle of international investors. This is the case, for example, of the Black Fund River, a hedge fund owned by the American Cargill Agro industry from China, acquired ninety thousand hectares in Colombia for the production of cereals.

To some extent, China has established itself as a platform for land acquisition around the world, from which capital funds from different funds and international companies such as BioPalm Energy (Singapore), AmirgaGroup (India), Adeagro (USA), Bunge (USA), LDC - Louis Dreifus Commodities (based in Switzerland), TIAA-CREF (US pension fund), Brow Co. (Philippines), Tiba Agro (Brazil, Europe and USA), Terra Magna Capital (fund based in Luxembourg), etc.

Possibly, the assembly and operation of that platform must be linked to some kind of benefit and facility for the entry and exit of FDI in China, as well as support from development banks and government sector policies responsible for land management in the selling countries.

Of course, purchases may also be coming from branches of these transnational companies based in China or institutions that have little or nothing to do with agricultural activity, like gigantic pension funds from various countries.

In addition, the possibility of purchasing land via China must be considered as a way of capital entry into the local financial markets.

There are investors (funds and transnational agricultural companies) who, according to GRAIN data, purchased land from China, as well as the country destination of these investments.

Other countries also act as an international investment platform for land acquisition, such as the United Kingdom, United Arab Emirates, USA and, to a lesser extent, Germany.

The Quifel Group, based in Portugal, acquired one hundred and twenty-six thousand hectares in Sierra Leone, effecting the,

purchase from the United Kingdom, as did the Al-Falah Group, from Bangladesh, which via the United Kingdom acquired thirty thousand hectares in Tanzania. Purchases from Afriagro (Portugal),,; Betexco (Nigeria) and HassadFood (Qatar) departed from the United Arab Emirates, acquiring land in Angola, Benin and Australia, respectively.

Olam International, a non-resident Indian company based in Singapore, from the USA made land purchases in Gabon and Argentina. From Germany, Al-Khorayef, a Saudi group.

Olam International also purchased land in Uganda (via Sweden), Uruguay (via Thailand), Mozambique (via France) a,nd Russia (via Nigeria).

Olam is one of the world's largest commodities brokers and has been investing in contract farms and agriculture, particularly in Africa and Latin America, being present in 65 countries. It has world leadership in several businesses, such as cocoa, coffee, cashew, wood, sesame products, rice and cotton. China, in addition to the funds and companies mentioned above, it seems that this triad is what drives the increase in acquisition of land in sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America and Australia. Such is the nature of investments made by groups such as Shanghai Pengxin Group Co. Ltd.¹⁹ and by COMPLANT.

Shanghai Pengxin Group recently announced the purchase of land in the Brazil, Bolivia (via Argentina) and New Zealand (via India) and COMPLANT acquired land in Jamaica (via Argentina), in Madagascar (via USA), in Sierra Leone (via Portugal) and in Benin (via Saudi Arabia).

In these operations, there is clear preponderance of Chinese capital (private and public, respectively), in a explicit strategy, mainly by COMPLANT, to guarantee China strategic sources for the supply of foodstuffs and mineral resources.

An example of this is the performance of Hua Lien International, a subsidiary of COMPLANT, which announced plans to establish a joint venture with China-Africa Development Fund (\$ 5 billion fund) to establish investment projects .ethanol in several African countries from Benin.

In 2010, Wuhan Iron Steel Group, China's third largest steel producer, got government approval for two acquisition deals in Africa.

The National Development and Reform Commission, economic planning body China, granted permission to Wuhan Steel's plan to acquire the iron ore Solana in Madagascar, along with two other companies. The big Chinese steelmaker also planned to buy 60% of China Union shares Investment Co., which has an iron ore reserve in central Liberia.

These two acquisitions alone contributed a total of two billion tonnes of iron ore reserves, which reduced the company's dependence on imports. According to sources from the company itself, cited by the News Agency Xinhua, the goal of the Chinese company was to become self-sufficient in supplying iron ore in a maximum of five years.

As well as several other large Chinese steelmakers, the goal is to break the “monopoly” (in terms used by directors of Wuhhan Iron Steel) of the three major global companies in the sector, Rio Tinto, BHP Billiton and Vale do Rio Doce.

Vertically integrated networks have been established to enable raw materials are directed to the Chinese market, made possible by the construction railways, highways, storage structure, minimal technology transfer and the establishment of some durable and non-consumer goods companies on the African continent, bringing these economies closer to Chinese dynamics.

In Africa, the strategy still involves geopolitical issues, shifting the axis of on the continent to reduce the American and European presence in the region and the related access to natural resources.

Companies, funds and the Chinese government itself are acquiring land using other countries as the investment site. That is due to innumerable factors like:

- Chinese branches around the world are acquiring land in neighbouring countries, for logistical and specialization issues in certain line of activity;
- Local development banks facilitate the purchase via branches, aimed at attracting FDI; - making use of regional blocks to Chinese seek to find greater facilities in which Chinese investments in land purchases ;
- Funds and Chinese companies aim to “circumvent” some types of protectionism “anti China ”entering different countries through other investment platforms.

The fact is that, as we saw above, purchases from China that totalled approximately 3.5 million hectares. This area, added to the amount of land acquired by the Chinese from other countries - over 3.5 million hectares purchased via Saudi Arabia, Argentina, Australia, Singapore, Japan, India, Malaysia, USA, Portugal, France, United Kingdom, Sweden and France in different regions of the globe - puts China in the position of the largest land buyer on a world scale. In addition to Chinese central government, the main companies and funds involved in these purchases indirect are largely Chinese.

The acquisition of land by China worldwide tends to generate impacts on the target countries of this strategy, at the same time that it seems to constitute the of the iceberg, which articulates a component of a possible Chinese strategy for development as well as the search for internationalized capital for spaces of recovery.

The conjunction of these two complex processes imbues even more complicated the acquisition of land and fictitious capital, on the one hand, capturing the Chinese to this logic, and, on the other hand, indicating an attempt by China to take ownership of it in order to respond to its internal challenges of development.

The difficulties in elucidating the nature of these operations for the acquisition of land are aggravated by the international spread of a tangle of transactions speculative and hedge transactions, involving a large number of agencies financing institutions, pension funds, insurance companies, equity funds public and private companies, which operate in most mergers and acquisitions of companies, as well as the opening of new transnational ventures.

Resulting from high-risk businesses, new joint ventures are being created by the so-called players, in an aggressive movement of entrances and exits, whose modus operandi followed for the opportunity for immediate returns in the so-called seed capital, venture capital and private equity.

References

AMIN, Samir. Theorie et pratique do projet chinois de “socialisme de marché”. In: CENTRE TRICONTINENTAL. Socialisme et Marché: Chine Vietnam, Cuba. Paris: L’Harmattan, 2001, p.53-90.

GRAIN. Pension funds: key players in the global farmland grab, Junho de 2011(a). Disponível em: www.grain.org/article/entries/4287-pension-funds-key-players-in-the-global-farmland-grab

HART-LANDSBERG, Martin and BURKETT, Paul. China and Socialism. Market reforms and class struggle. New York: Monthly Review, 2005.

CENTRE TRICONTINENTAL. Socialisme et Marché: Chine Vietnam, Cuba. Paris: L’Harmattan, 2001

MACDONALD, Scott. The Game of Soybeans: Emerging Supply from South America. KWR Special Report, Nova York

TIEJUN, Wen et alii. China’s Real Experience. China’s Course of Industrialization: Eight Crisis and Subsequent soft landing in 60 Years. 2011. Mimeo.

XIAOPING, Deng. To uphold socialism we must eliminate poverty. 1987. http://www.china.org.cn/china/CPC_90_anniversary/201107/01/content228993949.htm.